

Covid-19, Muslim Community and Indian Medi

Dr. ShivajiJadhav

Assistant Professor,
Department of Journalism & Mass Communication,
Shivaji University, Kolhapur
Email- sgj.jc@unishivaji.ac.in

Abstract

The Covid-19 has caused a stir in the media around the globe, leading to a major disaster for the world. India is no exception; however the issue is how the media handles the situation. The role of media should be crystal clear in the wake of crisis, also positive to avert the present scenario of the nation. It is necessary to study whether the print, electronic and web media in India have fulfilled their national responsibility while airing the Covid-19. In this regard, the research paper sheds light on the method of journalism used by the Indian media in covering the Coronavirus situation. This is a study of how the Muslim community in the country was covered through various media, especially after the Tablighi tribe's program during the lockdown in Nizamuddin, New Delhi. The role of print, electronic and web media in this period has been examined and the issue of credibility of media in India has been discussed.

Key Words:

Covid-19, Mass Media, Muslim Community, Credibility.

Introduction

The Covid-19 has spread around the world. The virus has become a major obstacle to the development and progress of human society. Humanitarian damage to advanced nations such as Italy, United States and Britain is certainly a cause for concern. In India, the graph of virus spread is exponential. The unexpected rise has affected the nation on all fronts. The effect of this virus is visible on all levels of society. The media is also being affected and the impact will be far-reaching in coming days. In order to convey objective information to the society, the basis of information system must be strong in any situation. The free flow of information was interrupted due to lockdown across the nation, particularly with the discontinuation of print

media. The readers were prevented from obtaining objective information. To find a way out of this, the print media carried information based on web versions. The flow of information through electronic and web media is continuous and faster than ever before, but the haste of electronic media and the improper behavior of web media is a picture of society being somewhat alienated from reliable information. In the post-Covid-19 era, there is a likely situation where there could be a huge disparity in the information universe. Web media will take over instead of traditional media giving rise to social complexity. Although web media is highly prevalent in India, its credibility is comparatively low. Instead of constructive work, the media are more concerned about the social health issues. Therefore, it is expected that after Covid-19, the information system in India will raise many serious issues, both socially and economically.

Objectives & Data Collection

Two objectives have been put forward for the research paper presented. 1. To study the coverage of Indian media in the context of COVID-19 and 2. Find out the medium through which most fake news was disseminated during Covid-19. Secondary sources have been used for this research paper. Research conducted in various countries around the world, Corona's impact on the media and the corresponding information disseminated from various newspapers as well as official websites have been used as references. It is presented in the research paper by analyzing the information based on secondary sources. It is also based on some reference texts.

Review of Literature

Covid-19 is having a negative impact on the finances of media. Many sports competitions were postponed or abandoned to stop the spread of the Covid-19, which resulted in Lockdown situations. This has had an impact on the media economy. On the other hand, people are increasingly using online media for information. (Stefan Hall, 2020) A survey conducted in Vietnam, China and India has revealed that the economic crisis is bigger than health due to COVID-19. (Laura Oliver, 2020) The World Health Organization (WHO) had to intervene as the COVID-19 pandemic caused a worldwide outbreak. It is a fundamental right of every citizen to get accurate and objective information through the media. Unfortunately during this period, there was an attempt to spread fake news through the media. For this purpose, the World Health Organization issued guidelines on how to collect and transmit the news of this epidemic. (Robin

Pomeroy, 2020) if rumors are spread through the media, a fearful atmosphere is created in the society. This increases the risk of epidemics. If information is given objectively, then it helps to maintain proper law and order. Accurate distribution of information is a major challenge facing the media around the world. All the media are facing many issues in compiling the information of COVID-19. Ground reporting and diversity of information are also limited, especially in the Hotspot territories. Despite this the journalists around the world are risking their lives to get as much information as possible to the target group.

Print is reliable but the Electronic Media is fictitious

India has a glorious tradition of media. Equally important is the active contribution of the media to the emergence of India as the largest democracy in the world. Traditional, print, electronic and web media in India are expanding at all levels and even in the days of COVID-19, all these media outlets are carrying information in their own way. The print media in India has always been an active contributor to neutral and objective journalism since pre-independence times. After 1990, when India became a part of globalization, electronic media expanded in the country. This medium has also captured the minds and imagination of the Indian people. However, in recent times, some electronic media groups in India have come under great scrutiny for their religious coverage. Questions are being raised about the role of some electronic media in India in covering the Tablighi tribe in the context of COVID-19. A religious program of the Tablighi tribe was held in the Nizamuddin area of New Delhi. The event was attended by thousands of people from home and abroad. Some of the Tablighi tribes in the nation who attended the event were infected with Covid-19 due to immigrants. This resulted in a lot of commotion in the country. According to a PTI report, authorities across states have identified more than 6,000 people who attended the Nizamuddin Tablighi Jamaat congregation. The venue has now emerged as the biggest COVID-19 hotspot in the country. According to news agency ANI, Delhi Police in a joint operation conducted by Crime Branch and city government said 275 foreign nationalists who attended the Tablighi Jamaat congregation at Nizamuddin Markaz have been identified and quarantined. The 275 foreign nationalists include 172 from Indonesia, 36 from Kyrgyzstan and 21 from Bangladesh. A study by Ritika Jain (2020) found that the coverage of the Nizamuddin case in Delhi between April 29, 2020 and May 4, 2020 was based on fake news and non-factual coverage. It was also reported through various media outlets that the corona virus had spread

through the Tablighi tribe's program at Nizamuddi. However after this, it was reported that the corona virus was spread by Muslims in the country. This created an atmosphere of suspicion about Muslims. The video was picked up on news channels and went viral on social media. This was an attempt to create a negative atmosphere about Muslims in the nation. The lack of proper management of information through electronic media was the primary reason for situation.

From the very beginning, serious journalism has been practiced in the print media in India. The same thing came to the fore during the airing of COVID-19. This is one of the reasons why people still have faith in print media. Indeed, rumors have it on social media that newspapers could be a source of spread of COVID-19. Initially, no definite official information was available. The administration has not made any official disclosure regarding the spread of pandemic through newspapers. This has resulted in confusion in the minds of the readers. Meanwhile, newspaper distributors also panicked. After the spread of false news, the country's newspapers had to shut down production for a forcible time period. Regardless, various newspaper outlets were working tirelessly to convey objective information to the readers through e-papers and websites. Expert interviews conducted by Mohana Basu (2020) revealed the possibility of the virus spreading through newspapers. Newspaper headlines also surfaced in India after the World Health Organization expressed fears that the virus could spread through paper currency. Newspapers could also be a source of spread of COVID-19, therefore some guidelines have been issued by the WHO which includes use of hand sanitizers for handling newspapers. As a result, newspapers in India gradually started re-publishing. Unfortunately the extent of reading of newspapers has come down a lot during this period. Newspapers haven't been made available at home; readers cannot buy newspapers due to lockdown guidelines. However, there is no doubt in the minds of the readers about the level of information in the newspapers, which is the foundation stone of the Indian print media. The TRP of news channels have increased a lot during the period when newspapers were shut down. The use of online media also increased rapidly. Newspaper readers prefer news channels and web media to satisfy their hunger, but at the same time, the media was busy with broadcasting fake news and a special kind of religious agenda that could result in social harm. The COVID-19 era created skepticism about India's electronic and web media, nevertheless the print media managed to maintain its credibility.

Digital media lost credibility

Digital media has been known for negative publicity in India from the very beginning. In the early days, with few exceptions, digital media did not make much effort to increase its credibility. Largely used for political purposes, the media in India played a key role in setting up the Jan Lokpal movement in Delhi under the leadership of senior social activist Anna Hazare. AnkitLal (2018) has elaborated on the role of social media in this movement. After the message that political interests can be achieved through this medium, social media started being used for political gain. This has eroded the credibility of digital media. Thus media was started to be used as a medium for rumors, misunderstandings, misinformation, fake news, defamation, etc. This led to media being part of many kinds of conspiracies. Rumors spread through social media's like Whatsapp, that have led to some incidents of people being crushed by mobs due to the misconception that a gang of child abductors has come to the country. According to a report from Alice Samuels (2020), more than two dozen people were crushed to death by mobs in India due to rumors spread by WhatsApp by mid-2018. The rumors were spread through WhatsApp that a gang was working to kidnap children. As a result, strangers were crushed to death by the accusers. Eventually the consequences of this resulted in some of these incidents have shaken people's confidence on social media.

TikTok, Facebook, Helo on the radar

During the COVID 19 period, lot of fake news was spread on social media. Many posts, especially against the Muslim community, went viral on social media. Numerous fake videos, fake posts, tampered photographs conveying the message that the Muslim community is responsible for the spread of corona in India were deliberately spread using social media. Billy Perigo (2020) describes the fact that, being a Muslim in India was already dangerous, then arrived Coronavirus. Hash tags like 'Corona Jihad', 'Pakistan Connection', 'Tablighi Jamaat Virus' were used to defame the Muslim community as much as possible. Even social media platforms could not control the measure of it. As a result, widespread Muslim hatred spread throughout the country. 'TikTok' disseminated the most misleading information regarding COVID-19 in India. Muslims in the country did not use corona protection accessories. In fact, there was an attempt by Muslims to spread the Corona, with several videos circulating on the subject. According to Surabhi Agarwal (2020), the central government has issued notices to Tiktok, Facebook and

Helo. Tiktok is responsible for the major outbreak. This created resentment in Indian society. As a result, hashtags such as 'Ban TikTok India', 'Jihad FailataTikTok', 'Data Leak by TikTok' were used intensively on Twitter. Several videos spreading misconceptions about Muslims about Corona also went viral. After analyzing over 30,000 such videos on social media, hundreds of them contained misleading, hateful and blasphemous content about Muslims. These videos brought disrepute to Muslims throughout the nation. Misconceptions were spread and an atmosphere of suspicion was created in the minds of the society about ordinary Muslims. The primary reason for the cause of disruption was the use of social media in improper manner.

News of Nizamuddin incident in Delhi received most coverage in the mainstream media. The electronic media held special coverage to induce the public. The issues in this discussion were communicated to maximum people as possible through social networking sites. This created a rift among the Muslim community. According to Bhupen Singh (2020), although the Nizamuddin case is believed to be the cause, it does not seem to have been done in a planned manner. Corona's first case came to light in January 2020, but the central government did not take immediate action. Questions in this regard with this issue were not put forward by the mainstream media towards the government. Even during the lockdown, other religious practices occurred in various parts of the country. However, none of those religious practices received any criticism from the mainstream media as well as social media. Therefore, while covering the Nizamuddin case in the context of COVID-19, it was clear that the media was targeting the Muslim community. Those responsible include some electronic media as well as some social networking sites.

Conclusion

During the COVID-19 period, both positive and negative coverage was reported in the Indian media. The study found that the print media is doing relatively more responsible journalism compared to Digital Media. Electronic media, however, made it clear that the Muslim community was the primary target. Most of the Hindi news channels as well as some English channels have been spreading misconceptions about Muslims that the corona spread in India was due to the TablighiJamati program organized by the Muslim community in New Delhi. Inconvenient information went viral on social media by collecting false news as well as news analysis. The main three mediums Facebook, TikTok and Helo created lots of confusion about

the Muslims. WhatsApp was also a major culprit in the process. India is known worldwide for its secularism and religious harmony. Despite that attempts were made by some media platforms to tarnish this all-encompassing image of India. It has also well undermined the tradition of neutral, objective and fearless journalism.

References

1. AgarwalSurabhi (2020), Remove videos spreading Covid-19 lies: Govt to Social media platforms, <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/internet/remove-videos-spreading-Covid-lies-govt-to-cos/articleshow/75016940.cms>
2. BasuMohana (2020), Transmission of coronavirus through newspapers, currency possible but unlikely: Experts, <https://theprint.in/health/transmission-of-coronavirus-through-newspapers-currency-possible-but-unlikely-experts/386194/>
3. Billy Perrigo(2020), It Was Already Dangerous to Be Muslim in India. Then Came the Coronavirus, <https://time.com/5815264/coronavirus-india-islamophobia-coronajihad/>
4. Elyse Samuels (2020), How misinformation on WhatsApp led to a mob killing in India, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/politics/2020/02/21/how-misinformation-whatsapp-led-deathly-mob-lynching-india/>
5. Laura Oliver (2020), Most people see COVID-19 as an economic crisis first, health risk second, survey finds, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/03/Covid-19-public-perception-economic-health-crisis-coronavirus-pandemic-ipsos/>
6. LalAnkit (2017), India Social: How social media is leading the charge and change the country, Hachette India
7. Ritika Jain (2020), Covid-19: How fake news and Modi government messaging fuelled India's latest spiral of Islamophobia, <https://scroll.in/article/959806/Covid-19-how-fake-news-and-modi-government-messaging-fuelled-indias-latest-spiral-of-islamophobia>
8. Robin Pomeroy (2020), Facts, not fear, will stop COVID-19 - so how should we talk about it?, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/03/Covid-19-coronavirus-who-media-guidelines-stigma-language/>
9. Stefan Hall (2020), Empty stadiums and online streaming: how coronavirus is affecting the media industry, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/03/Covid-19-coronavirus-media-entertainment-sports/>
10. Singh Bhupen (2020), Media in the Time of COVID-19, Economic and Political Weekly, Vol. 55, Issue No. 16, <https://www.epw.in/engage/article/media-time-Covid-19>